

ATTITUDE OF POST GRADUATE HOSTLERS TOWARDS RAGGING WITH RESEPECT TO GENDER AND LOCALE

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Abstract

The present study is a descriptive one and survey method has been used by the investigator. The purpose of present research investigation is to find out the difference in the attitude of post graduate hostlers towards ragging. Sampling area for the present study comprises the students who are residing in different hostels of Lovely Professional University. The investigator has taken 180 postgraduate hostlers from different discipline (60 Science, 60 Management and 60 Arts) as sample for his investigation by using stratified random sampling technique. For collection of data the investigator has used Scale for Measuring Attitude of Post Graduate students towards Ragging constructed and standardized by the himself. For analysis and interpretation of data the investigator has used t-test.

Key Words: Attitude, Ragging, Hostlers

Introduction

Ragging today has assumed torturous, vulgar and inhuman forms that defy all norms of decency and morality. It has become bane for the civilized and educated society. Moreover, Ragging has become a form of abuse of educational institutions. With ragging becoming a national issue affecting thousands of students across India, the Hon'ble Supreme Court of India too could not remain silent and has seriously condemned the issue. Hon'ble Supreme Court, while exercising its jurisdiction under Articles 32 and 142 of the Constitution of India, has laid down broad guidelines for colleges and educational institutes to prevent ragging. Very briefly, these guidelines are:

- Anti-ragging movements to be initiated by all colleges and educational institutes;

- Undertakings to be taken both from the freshmen and their parents/ guardians;
- Undertaking to be taken from seniors students and their parents/guardians too;
- Notices to be issued indicating where to approach for redressal in case of ragging;
- Management, principals and the teaching staff to have personal interaction with the freshmen;
- Practorial committees to be set up;
- Ragging- prone zones to be identified and carefully guarded;
- Society to be sensitised on the issue of ragging;
- Failure to prevent ragging to be constructed as an act of negligence;
- Hostels/accommodations to be carefully guarded;
- Migration certificates to mention whether the student ever indulged in ragging;
- Withdrawal of financial assistance to institutes where ragging incidents are reported;
- Students to first approach their colleges;
- Police not to follow a retributive approach while dealing with ragging culprits.

Recent steps taken by University Grants Commission:

University Grants Commission (UGC) has prepared draft regulations that intend to make it compulsory for students and their wards to state in writing that they are aware of the laws and punishment for ragging. It really requires a suggestion from an educational body to state the obvious that ragging is illegal and inhumane. There is a lot that teachers and medical professionals can do to prevent our students from being dragged into this cycle of brutality- either as a perpetrators or as victims. Ideally students can be counselled before they join college-or any line of study to ensure that they are mentally and physically capable of completing the course and succeeding in that particular line. This is standard practice to filter out a medically or physically unfit candidate from joining the armed forces. Interventions need to be two pronged. Ragging is a violation of Human Rights. As per the UGC Regulations, 2009, 'Ragging' constitutes one or more of any of the following acts:

- Any conduct by any student or students whether by words spoken or written or by an act which has the effect of teasing, treating or handling with rudeness a fresher or any other student;
- Indulging in rowdy or undisciplined activities by any student or students which causes or is likely to cause annoyance, hardship, physical or psychological harm or to raise fear or apprehension thereof in any fresher or any other student;

First, there should be stronger deterrents to ragging in the form of rules and strict punishments (akin to those for cheating in exams) accompanied by more vigilant monitoring of places and situations (such as isolated hostels and private hostels) where students are at risk of being ragged. However, it is not enough to focus on punishments alone. Ragging in India's education is widespread. Media has been reporting various instances of suicides, violence, physical injuries, sexual abuse and psychological disorders, resulting because of ragging. Beyond media's reach and authorities' attention, lakhs of students. Every year are being forced to go through this inhuman and barbaric experience. Issue has been attended by Judiciary. Legislatures have debated over ragging. Executive has been issuing circulars against ragging and media has been sensitive enough towards this evil. But the realities regarding ragging are still the same. Reported cases of ragging are only the tip of the iceberg of what is actually happening in numerous educational institutions across India. In reality, the number of unreported cases of ragging is much more than the cases reported by the media. It is often argued that measures to eliminate ragging should go beyond law, but it is equally reasonable to believe and argue that through Law's intervention, ragging can be effectively curbed and uprooted, as has been the case in countries like Canada and Japan. The problem of ragging needs to be approached with a human rights perspective and the question of ragging should be addressed as a concern of Education Law, as recommended by the United Nation Special.

Major cases found in India

- On 7 March 2009, Aman Kachroo, 19, a first year student of Dr Rajendra Prasad Medical College, Tanda, Kangra, HP, India, had repeatedly complained to his parents about the brutal ragging that took place on the Medical College campus — often by completely drunk third-year students. On Friday night and Saturday morning (March 6-7, 2009), the boy was beaten so badly that he died of brain haemorrhage
- On 18 September 2007, Durgesh Shukla hanged himself from a ceiling fan in his hostel room in Pioneer College, Bhopal. He blamed seniors in his suicide note.
- On 20 September 2007, Chetan Raj, 18, committed suicide in Mysore. His body was found hanging from the roof of his lodge room. He had already complained to his parents that he was being ragged in his college.

- On 8 August 2007, Manjot Singh, an MBBS student, committed suicide by consuming a poisonous substance. He did so at his residence in Chandigarh, due to ragging in his hostel at the Government Medical College, Chandigarh
- In November 2006, S. P. Manoj committed suicide in his hostel room at the Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Technology, Hyderabad.
- On 5 November 2006, Azad Nair, 22, a cadet at the Officer's Training Academy(OTA) in Chennai. He had hanged himself from the fan of his room. Prior to his suicide he had told his brother Soumendu over telephone that he was being ragged and humiliated at the OTA and he had pleaded to his father Padmanabhan Nair to rescue him from the OTA.
- On 14 December 2005, C Abraham, a first year engineering student, hanged himself to death at his residence in Hyderabad. In his suicide note, he mentioned that he was not interested in studies. His parents suspected that his suicide to be a result of ragging.
- On 5 December 2005, Sridhar, 18, hanged himself to the ceiling fan in his hostel room in Chennai. In the English press, only one newspaper in Mumbai reported the incident.
- On 11 October 2005, Amit Sahai committed suicide by jumping before an approaching train in Jalandhar. He was a student of NIT Jalandhar, Punjab. In his suicide note he blamed nine senior students of the National Institute of Technology, Jalandhar for having mercilessly ragged him.
- In July 2005, Kamlesh Sarkar, 19, committed suicide in a private hotel management institute in Kalyani, Nadia district, West Bengal. The police filed an unnatural death case and not one of ragging.
- On 19 December 2004, Mohan Karthik Tripathy,19, hanged himself from a ceiling fan in his hostel room at the SKR Engineering College in Tambaram, Tamil Nadu. His written complaint about ragging to the college authorities had gone unheeded. He had been forced to bathe in his own urine.
- In June 2004, Sushil Kumar Pandey, 18, hanged himself to death after the humiliation of being paraded naked by his seniors at the Madan Mohan Malviya Engineering College, Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh.
- In September 2002, Anup Kumar, 19, committed suicide by hanging himself from a ceiling fan at his residence in Kanpur. In his suicide note, Anup said that he was going through mental agony due to the sexual harassment by second-year students of the

Institute of Engineering and Technology, Lucknow, in the name of ragging. Through this study an attempt has been made by the investigator to find out the difference in the attitude of post graduate hostellers towards ragging and the reasons behind this mental trauma.

Objectives

- To find out the difference in the attitude of post-graduate science hostellers towards ragging with respect to gender and locale
- To find out the difference in the attitude of post-graduate management hostellers towards ragging with respect to gender and locale
- To find out the difference in the attitude of post-graduate arts hostellers towards ragging with respect to gender and locale

Hypotheses

- There exists significant difference in attitude of post-graduate science hostellers towards ragging with respect to gender and locale
- There exists significant difference in attitude of post-graduate management hostellers towards ragging with respect to gender and locale
- There exists significant difference in attitude of post-graduate arts hostellers towards ragging with respect to gender and locale

Methodology

The present study is a descriptive in nature and survey method has been used by the investigator. Sampling area for the present study comprises the students who are residing in different hostels of Lovely Professional University. The investigator has taken 180 postgraduate hostlers from different discipline (60 Science, 60 Management and 60 Arts) as sample for his investigation by using stratified random sampling technique.

Tool used

For collection of data the investigator has used an *Attitude Scale Towards Ragging* constructed and standardized by the investigator in 2011

Statistical Technique Used

For analysis and interpretation of data the investigator has used t-test .

Results and Discussion

Result pertaining to the difference in attitude of post-graduate science male and female hostellers towards ragging

To find out the difference in attitude of post-graduate male and female science hostellers towards ragging, t-ratio was computed and the result is presented in the table no.1

Table no.1
Result of t-test on Attitude of post-graduate science male and female hostellers
Towards ragging

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEd	t-ratio	Result
Science Male	30	130.6	17.93	4.63	1.95	Insignificant
Science Female	30	139.6				

Level of significance 0.05=2.00, Level of significance 0.01=2.66

From the table no.1, it is observed that the calculated t-ratio is 1.34 which is not significant at both levels. Therefore, it can be interpreted that there exists no significant difference in the attitude of post-graduate science hostellers towards ragging. Thus, Ho is accepted.

Result pertaining to the difference in attitude of post-graduate urban male and female science hostelers towards ragging

To find out the difference in attitude of post-graduate urban male and female science hostelers towards ragging, t-ratio was computed and the result is presented in the table 2

Table no.2

Results of t-test on Attitude of post-graduate urban male and female science hostelers towards ragging

Locality	N	Mean	SD	SEd	t-ratio	t-ratio
Urban Male	15	130.2	99.42	36.30	0.25	Insignificant
Urban Female	15	139.6				

Level of significance 0.05=2.04, Level of significance 0.01=2.75

The table no.2 depicts that the obtained t-ratio is 18.9 which is greater than the table value at both levels i.e.0.05 and 0.01 levels. It reveals that there exists significant difference in attitude of post-graduate urban male and female science hostelers towards ragging. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted.

Result pertaining to the difference in attitude of post-graduate rural male and female science hostelers towards ragging

To find out the difference in attitude of post-graduate rural male and female science hostelers towards ragging, t-ratio was computed and the result is presented in the table 3

Table no.3

Results of t-test on Attitude of post-graduate rural male and female science hostelers Towards ragging

Locality	N	Mean	SD	SEd	t-ratio	Result
Rural Male	15	139.6	14.8	5.41	1.61	Insignificant
Rural Female	15	130.9				

Level of significance 0.05=2.04, Level of significance 0.01=2.75

It is an evident from the table no.3 that the calculated t-ratio is 134.0, which is found to be significant at both levels i.e.0.05 and 0.01 levels. It can be interpreted that there exists a significant difference in attitude of rural male and female post-graduate science hostellers towards ragging. Thus, Ho is accepted.

Result pertaining to the difference in attitude of post-graduate male and female management hostellers towards ragging

To find out the difference in attitude of post-graduate male and female science hostellers towards ragging t-ratio was computed and the result is presented in the table 4

Table no.4

Results of t-test on Attitude of post-graduate male and female management hostellers towards ragging

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEd	t-ratio	Result
Management Male	30	134.3				

Management Female	30	137.5	58.69	15.15	0.21	Insignificant
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Level of significance 0.05=2.00, Level of significance 0.01=2.66

The table no.4 shows that the calculated t-ratio is 1.36, which not significant at both levels of significance. So it can be interpreted that there exists no significant difference in the attitude of post-graduate male and female management hostelers towards ragging. Thus, H_0 is accepted.

Result pertaining to the difference in attitude of post-graduate urban male and female management hostelers towards ragging

To find out the difference in attitude of post-graduate urban male and female management hostelers towards ragging, t-ratio was computed and the result is presented in the table 5

Table No.5

Results of t-test on Attitude of post-graduate urban male and female management hostelers towards ragging

Locality	N	Mean	SD	SEd	t-ratio	Result
Urban Male	15	139.9	10.3	3.77	1.31	Insignificant
Urban Female	15	135.0				

Level of significance 0.05=2.04, Level of significance 0.01=2.75

The table no.5 depicts that obtained t-ratio is 1.31 and which is less than table value at both levels. It implied that there is no significant difference in attitude of post-graduate

urban male and female management hostelers towards ragging. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted.

Result pertaining to the difference in attitude of post-graduate rural male and female management hostelers towards ragging

To find out the difference in attitude of post-graduate rural male and female management hostelers towards ragging, t-ratio was computed and the result is presented in the table no. 6

Table no.6

Results of t-test on Attitude of post-graduate rural male and female management hostelers towards ragging

Locality	N	Mean	SD	SEd	t-ratio	Result
Rural Male	15	128.7	14.7	5.36	2.10	Insignificant
Rural Female	15	140.0				

Level of significance 0.05=2.04, Level of significance 0.01=2.75

The table no.6 depicts that obtained t-ratio is 86 and which is found to be significant at both levels.. Therefore, It can be revealed that there exists significant difference in attitude of post-graduate rural male and female management hostelers towards ragging. Thus, null hypothesis is rejected.

Result pertaining to the difference in attitude of post-graduate arts male and female hostelers towards ragging

To find out the difference in attitude of post-graduate arts male and female hostelers towards ragging-ratio was computed and the result is presented in the table no.7

Table no.7

**Results of t-test on Attitude of post-graduate male and female arts hostelers
 towards ragging**

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEd	t-ratio	Result
Arts Male	30	142.0	14.5	3.24	1.33	Insignificant
Arts Female	30	141.5				

Level of significance 0.05=2.00, Level of significance 0.01=2.66

From the table no.7 it is observed that the calculated t-ratio is 1.33 which is not significant at both levels. Therefore, it can be interpreted that there exists no significant difference in the attitude of post-graduate arts male and female hostelers towards ragging. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted.

Result pertaining to the difference in attitude of post-graduate urban male and female arts hostelers towards ragging

To find out the difference in attitude of post-graduate urban male and female hostelers towards ragging, t-ratio was computed and the result is presented in the table no.8

Table No.8

**Results of t-test on Attitude of post-graduate urban male and female arts hostelers
 towards ragging**

Locality	N	Mean	SD	SEd	t-ratio	Result
Urban Male	15	146.1				

Urban Female	15	141.2	11.6	4.25	1.41	Insignificant
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Level of significance 0.05=2.04, Level of significance 0.01=2.75

From the table no.8, it is observed that our obtained t-ratio is 32 which is greater than the table value at both levels. It can be interpreted that there exists significant difference in attitude of post-graduate urban male and female arts hostelers towards ragging. Therefore, null hypothesis is accepted.

Result pertaining to the difference in attitude of post-graduate rural male and female arts hostelers towards ragging

To find out the difference in attitude of post-graduate rural male and female hostelers towards ragging, t-ratio was computed and the result is presented in the table no.9

Table No.9

Results of t-test on Attitude of post-graduate rural male and female arts hostelers towards ragging

Locality	N	Mean	SD	SEd	t-ratio	Result
Rural Male	15	137.9	13.1	4.7	0.61	Insignificant
Rural Female	15	140.8				

Level of significance 0.05=2.04, Level of significance 0.01=2.75

From the table no.9, it is observed that our obtained t-ratio is 21.4 which is found to be significant at both levels i.e.0.05 and 0.01 levels. Therefore, it can be interpreted that there exists significant difference in attitude of post-graduate rural male and female arts hostelers towards ragging. Thus, null hypothesis is found to be accepted.

Main Findings and Conclusion:

- There exists no significant difference in the attitude of post-graduate male and female science hostelers towards ragging. In other words, both male and female post-graduate science hostelers display similar type of attitude towards ragging. Moreover, most of the private institutions offer different type innovative causes and students taken admission in certain norms and conditions it has been already mentioned that ragging is prohibited.
- There exists no significant difference in the attitude of urban male and female science hostelers towards ragging.
- There exists no significant difference in attitude of rural male and female science hostelers towards ragging. The possible reason might be that the rural female hostelers believe that ragging is bane for society. They belong to simple families and they don't give importance to this anti-social act.
- There exists no significant difference in the attitude of post-graduate male and female management hostelers towards ragging, reason being that they support Supreme Court law the students who are involve in ragging-they might be expelled. The possible reason could be that wards of affluent families usually study in management (In this study, it is more so the data being collected from Lovely Professional University)
- There exists no significant difference in attitude of urban male and female management hostelers towards ragging.
- There exists no significant difference in attitude of rural male and female management hostelers towards ragging.
- There exists no significant difference in the attitude of post-graduate male and female arts hostelers towards ragging.
- There exists no significant difference in attitude of urban male and female arts hostelers towards ragging.
- There exists no significant difference in attitude of rural male and female arts hostelers towards ragging.

Suggestions

- The sample size can be enlarged to reaction more concrete results.
- A similar study can be conducted in different areas of the Punjab state and other states of India.
- A comparative study can be done on the attitude of hostellers and non-hostellers towards ragging.
- Similar study can be conducted on undergraduate level hostellers.
- Similar study can be conducted on Government institutions as well.

Recommendations

Anti-ragging movements should be initiated by the institutions right from the time of advertisement for admissions.

- The prospectus, the forms for admission and/or any other literature issued to aspirants for admission must clearly mention that ragging is banned in the institution and any one indulging in ragging is likely to be punished appropriately with punishment which may include expulsion or suspension from the institution or class for a limited period or fine with a public apology.
- The punishment may also take the shape of: (i) withholding scholarships or other benefits (ii) debarring from representation in events (iii) withholding results (iv) suspension or expulsion from hostel or mess, and the like.
- The institutions which are introducing such a system for the first time shall ensure undertakings being obtained from the students and their parents/guardians already studying in the institutions before the commencement of the next educational year/session.

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